

THE CONCEPT OF THE NEIGHBORHOOD: ESSENCE AND BASES OF FORMATION

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Abstract One of the most common forms of democracy is the self-government of citizens. Neighborhoods are the main link of the self-government system of citizens in Uzbekistan. The socio-philosophical basis of the formation and development of the neighborhood institution was studied in this research work. The scientific and theoretical foundations of the evolution of local state administration in the Republic of Uzbekistan have been studied.

Key words: Decentralization, institutionalization, scientific-methodological, encyclopedia, "Hayrat ul-Abror", Celsky Shod, democracy, guzar, community, elat, elod.

In the developed countries of the world, decentralization processes aimed at the distribution of powers from the upper management level to the lower level and increasing the participation of the general public are taking place. These processes show that it is impossible to implement democratic reforms in the system of representative state administration without public participation, contrary to centralized management methods and the interests of the population. It should be noted that if the local government is considered as a structure that tries to realize the interests of its voters, the local units are approached as a means of providing services and providing the interests of all categories of society. Also, the process of institutionalization of representative bodies of local state power is delayed. Today, improvement of the system of representative bodies of local state power is one of the urgent issues.

In Uzbekistan, the neighborhood institute was established in 1998, and they have the right to manage it in the local area office. It was introduced in the new political administration in order to provide rental in local areas in cooperation with other human resources and other areas.

The latest practices in the local areas, human resources and working status of the area office committee were analyzed and local hours were established as the largest extension of local area management. The neighborhood institute, in its activity, has become a better representation of the internal affairs of local regions and the development of socio-philosophical foundations.

Currently, the neighborhood institute has more than 160 structural structures across Uzbekistan. This institute aims to support young people, individuals, and families, and provides opportunities to learn interpersonal relationships, free choices, social interaction, and mutual respect.

The Neighborhood Institute, with the intention of providing convenient local area services to every person in Uzbekistan, develops its socio-philosophical foundations, strengthens interpersonal relations, and shows people an unforgettable space.

Currently, research centers of developed countries are carrying out scientific research on the transfer of additional new tasks from the central authorities of the state to the local authorities. Given that the status of local representative bodies is higher than local executive management bodies, they are becoming a public service that serves to satisfy the needs of the

population. As a result, the democratic system of territorial representation shows that it is improving. In particular, in the Anglo-Saxon school, it is emphasized that each local unit should participate in defining the tasks aimed at the development of public administration institutions, as well as developing a program of actions based on these goals and planning the administration.

In our country, it is important to increase the effectiveness of the representative bodies of local state power, to improve the participation and control of the public in it. After all, the intended goal can be achieved only when programs, laws, and decisions are implemented in real life and the society is cleansed of various vices" [1]. This is due to the fact that the powers and duties of local representative authorities require serious reforms. The effective functioning of local executive power largely depends on the influence of local representative bodies. Firstly, it is important to identify and prevent a number of situations that are an obstacle to the control of local representative bodies in ensuring the implementation of decisions by local executive authorities, and secondly, to scientifically research the observed shortcomings in the process of increasing the level of participation of the public through their representatives in local governance. is considered

The first elements of important processes in state administration were developed in ancient times, and in the works of Plato, Aristotle and Cicero, they were interpreted as the central and only mechanism of governance and the process carried out mainly by leaders, but by the new era, such views have changed. . For example, in the works of G. Jefferson, J. Locke, J. Rousseau, A. de Tocqueville, and J. Mill, the political significance of the institution of local government, the social nature of local self-government is highlighted. In the works of Abu Nasr Farabi, Nizamulmuluk, Amir Temur, Alisher Navoi and other thinkers in the East, it is emphasized that the criterion of justice and consultation with the council should be strictly followed in the implementation of the management process.

A number of studies devoted to the study of one or another aspect of the theory and practice of local self-government have been carried out in the world political sciences of the new era. In particular, the works of Western scientists I. Bentham, H. Shtimpfl, O. Roy, E. Harloff, H. Aldelfer, A. Gasser, S. Duncan and L. Toni are the local management process and self-management. takes an important place in the consideration of the theoretical principles of organization. However, these works are mainly intended for state administration with a federal form of structure, and have not been studied from the point of view of administration with a unitary form of structure.

From the scientists of the CIS: G.V. Barabashev, V.I. Vasiliev, A.A. Zamotayev, S.V. Korolev, A.G. Gladishev, E.A. Utkin, Ye.S. Shugrina, R.V. Babun, N.V. Postovoy, A.N. Shirokov, A.F. Denisov, V.N. Ivanov and I. Patrushev "local government " concept: state and territorial management processes; local government theory and practice; municipal management methodology, cooperation with state authorities; Concepts such as the organization of local self-government and its organizational foundations are revealed.

Thoughts and ideas on the effective organization of state administration in Uzbekistan in the works of President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev served as a scientific and methodological basis for this research work. Also, the theoretical issues of local state authorities in our country are widely covered in the researches of scientists such as: Sh. Jalilov, I. Jurayev, Yo. Ollamov, O. Khusanov, D. Bekchanov, Sh. Fayziyev and S. Khidirov. In the works of these researchers, the main

attention is paid to the organizational and legal basis of the activity of the local government, in which the local management is interpreted more normatively.

Also, in the scientific researches of Sh. Pakhrutdinov, K. Kuronboyev, S. Saidolimov, N. Jurayev, C. Jurayev, F. Ravshanov, V. Kuchkorov, U. Idivov, Sh. Otakulov, N. Kolkanov and other scientists, public administration and political processes are viewed from different points of view. In the works of Kolaversa, R. Jumayev, A. Japilov, M. Turakulov, B. Jurayev and Kh-Jurabekova, special attention is paid to the importance of local state power in the democratization of state administration and the formation of civil society, as well as theoretical aspects related to the decentralization process. Mahalliy boshqaruvni samarali tashkil etishda davlat hokimiyati bilan fukarolar, keng jamoatchilik va fukarolik jamiyati institutlarining hamkorligi buyicha J. Mavlonov, R. Jurayev, Sh. Yakubov kabi olimlar tomonidan ilmiy tadqiqotlar amalga oshirilgan. Xususan, R. Jurayev tomonidan umumdavlat va hududiy manfaatlar mutanosibligiga erishishda mahalliy hokimiyat organlari mas'uliyatini kuchaytirish,

Sh. Yakubov tomonidan esa, siyosiy partiyalarning xalk deputatlari mahalliy Kengashlari bilan hamkorligi masalalari yoritib berilgan.

Shuningdek, A. Dadasheva, A. Tulaganov, A. Yuldoshev, S. Muratayev, A. Maxmudov, Yangibayev, Z. Isroilova va boshka olimlarning ilmiy tadqiqotlarida mahalliy davlat hokimiyati vakillik organlari faoliyati tadqiq etilgan. Jumladan, Z. Isroilovning tadqiqotida mahalliy vakillik organlari faoliyatining samaradorligini baxolash mexanizmlari,

S. Muratayevning ilmiy izlanishida mahalliy vakillik organlarining funksiyalari, A. Maxmudov tomonidan esa, mahalliy vakillik organlarining nazorat faoliyatini amalga oshirish jarayonida yuzaga keladigan konstitusiyaviy-xukukiy munosabatlar tadqiq etilgan.

A number of scientific studies have been carried out in our country, which covered one or another aspect of the activities of local authorities. At the same time, while organizational transformation processes are taking place in the executive power and local councils, the need for scientific literature aimed at distinguishing the mutual functions of both powers is felt even more. Therefore, it is important to carry out scientific researches, conduct researches and analyze them to improve the efficiency of local Councils of People's Deputies.

After the independence of our country, a lot of work was done in a short period of time. During these years, a lot of work has been done in our country to reform the management system in order to transition from a strong state to a strong society. Also, the activity of neighborhoods has discovered a completely new meaning, and in the world experience, the only unique management institution called neighborhood exists only in us.[2]

The President of our country, Sh. M. Mirziyoyev, said, "... today the neighborhood needs to emerge as a great social force. Because activists, elders who have seen a lot, and our experienced intellectuals, if they want, they are able to solve any problem in cooperation with the public, and guide young people who have made mistakes[3] led to the period.

Mahalla, the brightest manifestation of the self-governing bodies, is recognized as the foundation and support of the civil society.

Also, at the initiative of the President, 2022 was declared as the "Year of Honoring Human Value and Active Neighborhood", and the project of the state program was prepared based on the new strategy. More than 17,000 suggestions were received from residents during open discussions. They were classified and summarized, and the draft program was filled with

more than 300 initiatives. The head of our state expressed his gratitude to our people for such activity, trust and concern for reforms.

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